

HYBRID COMPOSITES OF GLASS FIBERS AND SUGARCANE BAGASSE FIBERS FOR APPLICATION IN POLYMERIC TILES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is the obtaining of hybrid polyester composites reinforced with glass fibers and sugarcane bagasse fibers, evaluating their mechanical and water absorption properties, focusing on the application in polymeric tiles. Initially, the natural fibers were treated in NaOH solution and the composites were produced in plates form, from which the specimens were cut. After performing the tests, the best hybrid composite was selected and compared with the composite with 100% synthetic fibers, so that it was possible to state that it is feasible to produce polymeric tiles with hybrid composites of fiberglass and fibers of sugarcane bagasse.

KEYWORDS

sugarcane bagasse fibers; Natural fibers; Mechanical properties; Sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

The subjects related to environmental impacts and preservation are the most frequent in current studies, especially in civil engineering, since construction is one of the industries that produces more solid waste and consumes more natural resources (Roth; Garcias, 2009). In this context, tiles are one of the indispensables several materials that are produced and used in civil construction, but they are heavy and difficult to handle, increasing construction costs, since more reinforced structures are needed to support the additional loads. In addition, when they are compared to other types of existing materials, it is possible to notice their low tensile and flexural strength, which causes their easy rupture (Araújo; Moral; Altides, 2008).

Polymer tiles are composite materials that have become a great alternative to solve the problems of low tensile strength and bending. These materials have a combination of two or more elements, usually a matrix and a reinforcement, such that their properties together are greater than their individual properties. Thus, polymer matrix composites are very present in civil construction, as they have a relatively low manufacturing cost and express excellent physical characteristics and mechanical, in addition to being lightweight and durable, which makes them extremely competitive in the market. Polymer matrices have replaced several conventional products as a way to improve the specific characteristics of each material manufactured, transforming them into raw material for the production of elements used in constructions, such as tiles for example (Vieira; Scallop; Carvalho, 2016).

Fiberglass is a material widely used as a hybrid reinforcement in polymeric composites of civil construction, because it presents an excellent mechanical resistance when added to the polymer matrix, having an excellent durability and low specific weight (Kemerich et al., 2013). Despite that, several researches have been carried out to verify the substitution of synthetic fibers by natural fibers in the polymeric composition. Fibers such as sugarcane bagasse, also known as lignocellulosic fibers, are made up of natural polymers such as lignin, hemicellulose, cellulose and among others, which are responsible for its main mechanical and physical properties. When compared with other natural fibers they may have a low tensile strength and lower modulus of elasticity, but they have a higher

resistance to moisture and low cost, in addition to being sustainable and degrading better in the environment (Sanchez et al., 2010).

To obtain a better fiber/matrix interaction, it is necessary to perform a chemical treatment on the natural fiber, aiming at the partial removal of lignin and hemicellulose (Sanchez et al., 2010). The alkaline treatment, usually using sodium hydroxide (NaOH), aims to increase the contact surface of the fibers, facilitating their interaction with the polymer matrix, consequently generating improvements in the mechanical properties of polymeric composites with reinforcement (Milani, 2015).

According to CONAB (2021), the sugarcane industry is one of the largest in the country, and the center of Goiás is one of the Brazilian regions that has more mills than extra in cane to obtain alcohol and sugar. As soon as the sugarcane juice is extracted in the mill, the bagasse is reserved and taken to the boiler to be burned, generating the steam necessary for the operation of the turbines that drive the power generators, which causes the burning in biomass and harms the environment (Nunes; Finzer, 2018).

Thus, the main objective was the study of obtaining hybrid composites of polyester and hybrid reinforcement of glass fibers and natural fibers of sugarcane bagasse, evaluating their performance and mechanical properties, focusing on the application in polymeric tiles. In this way, a different destination is provided to the agro-industrial material, in addition to contributing with a more sustainable material for civil construction.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, composite groups were produced in different proportions between synthetic and natural fibers and the objective was to verify which is the best hybrid composition to use natural fibers. These composition of hybrid composites was compared with the 100% fiberglass composite, in this way, it was possible to verify its efficiency and evaluate a possible production of polymeric tiles with natural fibers.

Materials

The sugarcane bagasse fibers were supplied by Usina Goianésia S/A, located in the city of Goianésia-Goiás. The fibers were available in natura, with moist and in pieces of 1 to 10 cm. Glass fibers from Fiberglass Brazil were also used, in the form of a blanket of random fibers and with dimensions of 6 to 8 cm. And finally, isophthalic unsaturated polyester resin from Embrapol, which was used together with the MEK V50 catalyst, which is the curing agent.

Treatment and Thermogravimetric Analysis of Sugarcane Bagasse Fibers

The fibers were treated with a methodology developed by Libera Junior et al., (2019). Initially, the sieving process was first performed the fibers to remove particles that did not fit the desired dimensions, 6 to 8 cm. Then, the fibers were dried in an oven at 80 °C for 24 h. After the drying process, the fibers were immersed in hot water at a temperature of 100 °C for 2 h to remove dirt and impurities. After that, they were dried at room temperature for 48 h, followed by drying in an oven for 24 h at 100 °C.

The fibers were subjected to an alkaline solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) with concentration of 5% (w/v), for 24 h at room temperature. Subsequently, they were washed in running water until pH neutralization occurred, dried at room temperature for 48 h, and dried in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h. In the end of the treatment, the fibers were stored in a dry space to be not exposed to moisture. Figure 1 shows the natural fibers of sugarcane bagasse before and after the alkaline treatment.

Figure 1: Sugarcane bagasse fibers before and after the NaOH treatment process.

The thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) of in natura and treated sugarcane bagasse fibers were performed in an SDT Q600 equipment (TA Instruments) under an inert nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 100 mL/min. Before the analysis, the fiber samples were placed in the oven for 24 h at a temperature of 80 °C, so that all moisture was removed prior to the test.

After drying, the samples were stored in a closed container and remained at room temperature, protected from any moisture. Then, portions of 12 ± 0.5 mg of the samples were weighed, placed in an alumina crucible and analyzed under a heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 600 °C.

Obtaining the Composites and Preparation of the Specimens

Initially, the polymeric composites were produced in the format of plates in the dimensions of 200 mm x 220 mm, from where the specimens were extracted for the mechanical and water absorption tests. The composites were made through the manual lamination process, where the blankets of glass fibers and sugarcane bagasse were positioned in interleaved layers to form a hybrid composite with the two materials.

The polymeric composites were produced using a proportion of fibers in relation to the mass of the composite of 25% (w/w), a value established in accordance with the recommendations of NBR 16753 (2019), which refers to the requirements and test methods on flat plates, tiles and continuous domes of glass fiber reinforced polyester. For the production of the composites, only the blankets were made with the fibers of sugarcane bagasse, since the glass fiber blankets were available complete. In the procedure, the fibers were weighed and spread on a surface with the same dimensions as the plates, and then were pressed with a roller, in order to facilitate the assembly of composites.

The hybrid composites were produced using a joint stacking of 4 layers of fibers in different proportions (fiberglass and sugarcane bagasse). Thus, the reinforcement was divided into the proportions in percentage of 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 of the total volume that the composites reinforcement, that is, of the 25% of the ratio between the mass of the fibers and the total mass of the composite, as specified in NBR 16753 (2019) and as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Distribution of fiber layers in composite production.

Thus, the amount by mass (g) of the natural fibers were determined according to the density of the glass fiber, 2.5 g/cm³, and the fiber of sugarcane bagasse, 0.5 g/cm³, it was possible to obtain the 25% established by NBR 16753 (2019). Two proportion of hybrid composites was established in percentage of weigh, the first one of 50% of synthetic fiber and 50% of sugarcane bagasse fiber, and the second one in the proportion of 75% synthetic and 25% natural, in order to compare the results obtained and determine the best composition. This proportion was calculated in weight and Table 1 shows the number of fibers contained in the reinforcement and their respective percentages of glass fiber (V) and sugarcane bagasse fibers (B) in relation to the total weigh.

Table 1: Distribution of fibers in the reinforcement of each composite.

Composite	Distribution of layers	Total mass of the reinforcement fibers in relation to 25% of the composite mass (g)		Total volume of the reinforcement fibers in relation to 25% of the composite volume (%)	
		Glass	Sugarcane bagasse	Glass	Sugarcane bagasse
C1	[V] ₄	88.04	0.00	100	0
C2	[V ₂ /B ₁ /V ₁]	59.59	19.94	75	25
C3	[V ₁ /B ₂ /V ₁]	40.42	8.00	83	17
C4	[V ₁ /B ₂ /V ₁]	39.23	12.00	77	23
C5	[V ₁ /B ₂ /V ₁]	39.91	16.00	71	29

The composites were produced on a free surface and without imperfections. Initially, the surface was prepared with the position of a polyethylene film. The composite was then produced by placing the blankets one on top of the other, in an overlapping way, where each layer was impregnated individually, by means of manual lamination with the aid of a brush, by the solution of the polyester matrix, obtained through the mixture between the polyester resin and the curing agent. The resin/catalyst ratio used was 1.5 phr.

After establishing the number of blanket fibers, they were weighed and reserved. Considering that the reinforcement corresponds to only 25% of the composite, then the amount of resin corresponds to 75% of the total mass of the fibers and the curing agent is equivalent to 1.5% of the mass of the polyester resin. Table 2 below shows the amount of resin and catalyst that were used for the production of the composites, including their final mass after going through the curing process.

Table 2: Quantity of materials used in the production of composites.

Composite	Mass (g)		
	Resin	Healing agent	Final composite
C1	264.41	3.85	338.56
C2	238.54	3.59	305.18
C3	145.32	2.13	143.86
C4	153.55	2.37	193.04
C5	167.70	2.55	207.21

In Figure 3 it is possible to observe the schematic representation of how the materials used and the layers that formed the final composite were packed.

Figure 3: Stacking the layers of the final composite.

The plates were compressed using a weight sufficient to produce a load of 7.6 kPa. The plates were cured at room temperature for 24 h and were not submitted to the post-cure process.

After the production of the plates, specimens were cut according to the sizes required in the standards for the Tensile and Charpy Impact tests. The specimens for the tensile test were cut according to ASTM D3039, which are specific for polymer matrix composite materials, with dimensions of 200 mm x 25 mm x 3.0 mm. For the Charpy impact test, they were cut according to ASTM D6110, having specimens with dimensions of 125 mm x 12.7 mm x 3.0 mm. However, after the analysis of the equipment used for the tests, it was necessary to perform an adaptation in the specimen for the impact test, which now has the dimensions of 80 mm x 12.7 mm x 3.0 mm. Figure 4 shows the final dimensions of the specimens.

Figure 4: Dimensions of the specimens (mm) for the Tensile and Charpy Impact tests.

From each composite the total of 9 specimens were cut, 4 for the tensile test, 4 for the impact test and 1 for the water absorption test, resulting in 45 specimens. After being cut, the specimens were still sanded on their sides.

Mechanical Tests and Statistical Analysis

The Tensile tests followed the guidelines described in ASTM D3039, and the analyses were performed with the support of a universal machine for mechanical tests INSTRON 8801 that has a load cell of 100 kN, available at the University of Brasília – UnB. A total of 20 specimens were

tested, 4 of each composite with different proportions of synthetic and natural fibers, they were positioned in the grippers of the equipment with care to align the shaft with the direction of the test. Then, the claws were tightened and the pressure used was recorded, with a speed of 2 mm/min until the specimen rupture occurred, so that it was possible to obtain information such as the limit of tensile strength, deformation at break, and tensile modulus of elasticity. Figure 5 shows the composite positioned in the equipment before and after the rupture.

Figure 5: C2 composite positioned in the equipment before and after the Tensile test.

The Charpy Impact tests were performed according to ASTM D6110, using the PANTEC impact testing machine with a pendulum of 2.70 J, with a variation of ± 0.14 J. In this case, the specimens were adjusted in their length to 80 mm, so that it fit the equipment. After conclusion, the results were reported in terms of energy absorbed from the test body. Figure 6a shows the PANTEC equipment ready to be used, while Figure 6b shows the 4 specimens of the C1 composite already tested.

Figure 6: And PANTEC and the Specimens after the Charpy Impact test.

In the end, the results of the mechanical tests such as tensile modulus of elasticity, tensile and impact strengths were interpreted using ANOVA analysis of variance.

Thus, the 5 composites produced were arranged together with their respective results of each mechanical assay, containing 4 replicates and 20 results. Considering that there is only one question

variable and that the objective is to have only one result for each of the composites, at the end we obtained 5 averages, which were compared between them and statistically verified their equality.

The analysis of variance was performed using the SISVAR 5.6 software, by the comparative method of the means of the repetitions of each specimen by the Scott-Knott test at 5% probability.

Water Absorption

The tests were performed according to ASTM D570 to evaluate the water absorption of plastics. These tests were performed after conditioning five samples of the composites, which were dried in an oven for 1 h at a temperature of 105 °C to 110 °C. And only then was the immersion procedure performed for 24 h, in which the conditioned composites were placed in a container with water kept at a temperature of 25 °C. At the end, the samples were taken one at a time, the surface water was cleaned with a dry cloth and weighed immediately on an analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.001 g, so that it was possible to calculate the relative rate of the laminates when they were immersed. This procedure last for 22 days. During this time, the first weighing of the specimens was with 24 h, then with 7 days and then the process was repeated for another 2 weeks, with 2 weighing per week (1 every 72 h), so that at the end 6 weighing were added. After all, the percentages of water absorption in each composite were calculated, so that at the end it was possible to observe the behavior of the specimens in relation to humidity and determine which of them had the highest absorption index.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermogravimetric Analysis

The result of the thermogravimetric analysis of the sugarcane bagasse fibers in natura and treated with NaOH is presented in Figure 7 as a function of temperature. The first time mass loss occurs is due to the loss of water present in the fibers (~70 °C). The degradation of in natura fibers begins at approximately 290 °C, this corresponds to the second mass loss event, which is when the decomposition of natural fiber constituents such as lignin and hemicellulose occurs. And the last event refers to the thermal decomposition of cellulose that occurs, approximately, at 345 °C and 327 °C, in the untreated fiber and in the treated fiber, respectively. Due to the presence of lignin and hemicellulose, in natura fibers take a longer time to decompose, so their peak in Figure 7a is higher, while the peak of the treated fiber is lower, because it no longer contains these natural constituents.

Figure 7b shows that when performing the thermogravimetric analysis, the percentage of mass loss of the fiber treated with NaOH was lower than the mass loss of the fiber without treatment, which occurred between 200 °C and 400 °C. This happened because the treated fiber did not contain in its composition the natural constituents, or amorphous, causing there to be less loss (Lavoratti et al., 2013).

Figure 7: Thermogravimetric analysis of in natura fibers and fibers treated with NaOH.

Table 3 shows the approximate temperature at which the events of mass loss of in natura fibers treated with NaOH with a concentration of 5% (m/v) occurred. Considering that the 1st event refers to water loss, the 2nd is related to the degradation of the amorphous constituents of the fibers without treatment, since they are not present in the treated fibers, and the 3rd is associated with thermal decomposition.

Table 3: Approximate temperature of mass loss events.

Fibers	Temperature (°C)		
	1st event	2nd event	3rd event
In natura	70	290	345
Treated with 5% NaOH (m/v)	70	-	327

With the analysis performed, it is possible to affirm that the treatment of the natural fibers of sugarcane bagasse was done in the correct way, because observing the Figure 7 shows that lignin and hemicellulose were removed from the in natura fibers, which provided a better interaction of the fiber with the polyester matrix. Due to the removal of these components, the treatment with NaOH caused the contact surface of the fibers to increase and facilitate the fiber/matrix interaction, improving the mechanical properties of the composites produced.

Mechanical Tests

Tensile test

From the Tensile tests it was possible to obtain information such as the resistance limits and tensile modulus of elasticity shown in Figure 8. To represent in graph form, the average of the data obtained from each specimen was calculated, so that there was only one value for each composite. In addition, the standard deviations of each element are still presented along with the statistical analysis performed, understanding as statistically equal the values represented by the same letter, with *a* being the best, *b* the second best and so on.

Figure 8a shows that the composites C1 and C3 have the best tensile strength and are statistically equal to each other, with average strengths of 70.53 MPa and 69.57 MPa, respectively. The strengths of the C2 and C4 composites are also statistically equal and make up the second place of best strength, leaving the lowest result for the C5, which is composed of 71% fiberglass and 29% bagasse fibers. It can be stated that the composite with 100% synthetic fiber (C1) and the one that has the lowest amount of natural fiber (C3) are the ones that have the best result, due to the fact that it contains the largest amount of fiberglass, which in turn is known to have excellent mechanical properties, including high tensile strength (Ortenzi Júnior, 2007).

Regarding the obtaining of the modulus of elasticity presented in Figure 8b, it is possible to affirm that all obtained a good result, so much so that all are considered statistically equal, especially in C3 with 10.92 GPa and in C4 with 10.10 GPa. These composites are the ones that have the lowest amount of sugarcane bagasse fibers, which in turn is characterized by having a low modulus of elasticity (Sanchez et al., 2010).

Figure 8: Results of the Tensile test of the composites with standard deviation.

Table 4 presents the summary of the tensile test, in which the average values of the limits of strength, maximum deformation, modulus of elasticity and specific strength are exposed. The results of the statistical analysis of the resistance and the modulus of elasticity were also added to the table.

Table 4: Mean values of the mechanical properties obtained from the Tensile test.

Composites	Tensile strength (MPa)	Maximum deformation (%)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Specific strength (MPa/g/cm ³)
C1	70.53 ± 6.46 a	1.89 ± 0.62	09.92 ± 0.40 a	57.58 ± 5.27
C2	62.38 ± 2.67 b	1.11 ± 0.06	09.57 ± 0.37 a	48.46 ± 2.13
C3	69.57 ± 2.64 a	0.94 ± 0.05	10.92 ± 0.18 a	53.78 ± 3.05
C4	59.96 ± 3.73 b	0.90 ± 0.07	10.10 ± 0.85 a	47.09 ± 1.84
C5	47.09 ± 5.13 c	0.77 ± 0.13	09.60 ± 0.84 a	41.32 ± 3.08

Given the results obtained, it can be stated that C3, which contains the largest modulus of elasticity in tensile, is the most rigid composite and also the one that suffered the least elastic deformation. It also has a high strength, with only a 1.4% difference between it and C1, which is composed only of synthetic fibers. Considering these results and that this composite has 2 layers of glass fibers with 40.42 g, and 2 layers of sugarcane bagasse fibers with 8 g, this being the smallest proportion of natural fibers used, it can be concluded that this composite is the best in mechanical properties related to the tensile test.

Charpy Impact

From the Charpy Impact tests, it was possible to obtain values related to Impact Resistance, which can also be defined as impact energy, since it refers to the energy that the specimen absorbed at the time it suffered the rupture. Table 5 shows the mean of these values obtained for each composite, with the standard deviations and the statistical analysis performed.

Table 5: Mean values of the mechanical properties obtained from the Charpy Impact test.

Composites	Impact Resistance (J)
C1	17.75 ± 6.18 a
C2	13.00 ± 1.73 a
C3	06.25 ± 2.28 b
C4	07.25 ± 0.83 b
C5	15.50 ± 3.20 a

Figure 9 shows that the composites C1, C2 and C5 are statistically equal. Thus, leaving the lower values for C3 and C4, which are also considered equal statistically.

Figure 9: Charpy Impact strength of composites with standard deviation.

Although the fibers of sugarcane bagasse have low impact resistance, when natural fibers are treated with NaOH, their properties increase significantly, so that when they are added to the glass fibers, which have superior strength, form a hybrid composite with considerable properties (Santos; Sydenstricker; Amico, 2006).

Thus, after the analysis, it is possible to observe and affirm that the composites that most absorbed impact energy are those that present a greater amount, by mass, of fibers of glass and natural fibers of sugarcane bagasse in its composition, which consequently are also the heaviest and those with a greater thickness, making them more resistant to impact.

Water Absorption

After performing the water absorption test, one can obtain information from all composites and observe how they behaved when immersed in water for 22 days. Figure 10 shows the absorption index of each specimen, where it is clear that the highest absorption index belongs to C5, due to its composition being 2 layers of synthetic fibers and 2 layers of natural fibers and the latter being in large quantity (16 g), there were more empty spaces in the composite, which made it easier for the water to enter. And although C2 has a higher amount of sugarcane bagasse fibers (19.94 g), its absorption index was lower than C5, due to the fact that it contains one more layer of fiberglass in its composition (3 of synthetic fibers and 1 of natural fiber).

According to Sanchez et al. (2010), sugarcane bagasse fibers have a better moisture resistance than other natural fibers. Despite this, during the manufacture of the composites, the glass fibers formed the outer layers as a means of protection so that the water was not absorbed directly by natural fibers. However, according to Silva et al. (2008), when they are inserted into a hybrid composite in large quantities, as in case of C2 and C5, they are closer to the ends, increasing its void index and allowing water to be absorbed more quickly.

Figure 10: Water absorption index of the composites during 22 days.

Thus, it can be stated that the composite that absorbed the least amount of water was C1, which contains only synthetic fibers, leaving C3 and C4 with approximate values and with the best results of absorption, containing natural fibers in its composition. It is also noted that between C3 and C4, C4 was the one that stabilized and remained constant more quickly, but at the end of the 22 days C3 was the one that absorbed the least amount of water, leaving it with the best index after C1. This comparison also extends the amount of natural fibers that each one has, C3 contains 8 g and C4 contains 12 g, which is one of the reasons for C3 to achieve this placement.

According to Beraldo (2017), polymeric tiles with the presence of natural fibers have important characteristics in addition to reducing the environmental impact, such as the fact that the fibers act on the protection against solar rays, that is, because they have an excellent thermal insulation. However, many studies still claim that a tile composed of natural fibers can have low durability due to exposure to rainfall. Therefore, the tiles usually receive a layer of acrylic varnish, which prevents the absorption of moisture, increasing its durability (Rossignolo; Fabrício; Lima, 2007).

CONCLUSION

After the analysis of the results obtained, it can be concluded that it is technically feasible to use hybrid composites of fiberglass and natural fibers of the sugarcane bagasse to produce polymeric tiles. From the study, it was possible to evaluate the efficiency of the treatment of natural fiber in NaOH solution by means of thermogravimetric analysis.

The mechanical tests indicates that C3 composites present best results in relation to the other hybrid composites. Since they were composed by 25% of the reinforcement, for the most part, of synthetic fibers known for their excellent mechanical properties. In the tensile test, this composite was considered statistically equal the C1 composite, with a difference of only 1.4%, and its modulus of elasticity, which is the highest among those analyzed. Consequently, in the Charpy impact test, the C3 results were inferior to the other composites produced, absorbing only 6.25 J of energy at the time of rupture. Regarding the water absorption, it was noted what was already expected, the C1 (with 100% fiberglass) absorbed less amount of water, followed by C3, which was the composite with natural fibers that obtained better results, due to it low sugarcane bagasse in its composition. Because the higher the content of natural fibers, closer to the surface they stay, increasing the index of voids and absorbing more water, as happened with the composite C5.

In this way, it was assumed that C3 is the best composite with natural fibers of sugarcane bagasse, and it is possible to affirm that the production of polymeric tiles with the composition of 100% fibers synthetic can be replaced by a hybrid composition, composed of 17% fiber from sugarcane bagasse and 83% fiberglass. This change reduces the use of synthetic fibers and reuses natural fibers with renewable sources that would be discarded inappropriately, thus having an optimal contribution to the environment. Considering that the construction industry has sought more sustainable construction methods, it is evident that the production of hybrid polymeric tiles composed of glass fibers and fibers Natural is an environmentally beneficial, technically viable and financially attractive alternative.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper

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